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SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Theoretical background

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- Construction industry: one of the oldest industries but low productivity (Fulford and Standing, 2014)
- Supply chain management (SCM) has been identified as a key area for increasing productivity in this industry (Vrijhoef and Koskela, 2000)
- However, the peculiar characteristics of the construction industry make the application of traditional SCM practices a daunting task (Behera et al., 2015):
 - ▣ Temporariness and fragmentation of the supply network
 - ▣ Variability due to the large number of stakeholders and correlation to economic cycles
 - ▣ Traditional low orientation towards collaboration, change inertia
 - ▣ New challenges: fast track projects

SCM in Construction

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Different perspectives:

1. **SC Strategy:** advantages, barriers and enablers for partnership with suppliers (Venselaar et al., 2015)
2. **Logistics:** material flow management and warehousing (Childerkouse et al., 2003)
3. **Project Management:** pre-project phases (e.g., tendering) and project procurement in relation to the execution of the project (Khalfan et al., 2011)
4. **ICT** analysed the application of extended ERP, building information modelling (BIM) and eProcurement technologies
5. **Purchasing management:** importance of managing suppliers in the construction industry with modern purchasing management approaches (Van Lith et al., 2015)

Research Objectives

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1. Analyse SCM in the construction sector and its evolution over time
2. Highlight the most recent trends for each perspective
3. Draw the most promising future developments for the field

- Systematic Literature Review: rigorous and well-defined approach to review the literature in a specific domain
- Following the guidelines provided by the literature (Kitchenham and Brereton, 2013; Khan et al., 2003)

Context of the Study

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- SUCCESS Project
- The focus of the SUCCESS project is on reducing the negative impacts and cost of freight distribution in urban areas by improving the knowledge and understanding of freight distribution and service trips for the construction sector and by demonstrating the impacts in terms of transport and environmental efficiency

Sample

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- 641 articles published in Scopus-indexed journals on December 24th 2015 using the following criteria:
 - “Supply chain” and “construction” in title, abstract or keywords
 - Only articles in English
 - Only in the following domains: Business, Management and Accounting, Computer Science, Decision Sciences, Economics, Econometrics and Finance, Engineering, Environmental Science, Multidisciplinary, Social Science
 - No time restriction

Sample

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Journal	Total
Construction Management and Economics	26
Automation in Construction	20
Supply Chain Management	17
Journal of Construction Engineering and Management	14
Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management	14
International Journal of Project Management	12
European Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management	10

Keywords

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- Authors' + index keywords.
- 1670 keywords, 1070 keywords were excluded from the analysis because they were too generic or not relevant (e.g., “academic community”, “adoption”, “preference order”) or related to methodology
- The remaining 600 keywords were aggregated into:
 1. SC STRATEGY
 2. PROJECT MANAGEMENT
 3. LOGISTICS
 4. PURCHASING MANAGEMENT
 5. ICT
 6. SUSTAINABILITY (added)

Design

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Category	Keywords count
ICT	157
SC STRATEGY	92
<i>SUSTAINABILITY</i>	84
LOGISTICS	58
PROJECT MANAGEMENT	52
PROCUREMENT	52

Results: keywords over time

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Results: journal and categories

Keywords Factor Analysis

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EID	SCM	LOGISTICS	PM	PROCUREMENT	ICT	SUSTAINABILITY
2-s2.0-12444296913	0	0	0	0	1	0
2-s2.0-0000387917	2	4	0	1	4	1
2-s2.0-0041308391	2	0	3	1	0	0
2-s2.0-0034391513	2	0	0	1	0	0
2-s2.0-0033691188	4	0	3	1	1	0
2-s2.0-0033738551	4	0	1	2	1	0
2-s2.0-0034323345	0	0	1	0	0	4

Keywords Factor Analysis

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1998-2006

Factor	Eigenvalue
Factor1	1.269
Factor2	1.227
Factor3	1.077
Factor4	1.025
Factor5	0.780
Factor6	0.622

Varimax rotation

Variable	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4
SCM	-0.767	0.106	0.227	0.045
LOGISTICS	0.120	-0.736	0.411	-0.296
PM	0.074	0.790	0.367	-0.207
PROCUREMENT	0.022	0.003	0.082	0.951
ICT	0.765	0.083	0.216	0.081
SUSTAINAB.	0.025	-0.042	-0.865	-0.137

2007-2015

Factor	Eigenvalue
Factor1	1.497
Factor2	1.267
Factor3	0.932
Factor4	0.901
Factor5	0.733
Factor6	0.670

Varimax rotation

Variable	Factor1	Factor2
SCM	0.712	-0.218
LOGISTICS	-0.240	0.598
PM	0.401	0.443
PROCUREMENT	0.695	-0.023
ICT	-0.027	0.751
SUSTAINAB.	-0.536	-0.322

Keywords Factor Analysis

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Based on 2 factors, and no rotation

Citation Network

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Citation Network

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Main Path Analysis

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Chain of articles which have received the highest number of citations from other papers in the corpus

Main Path Analysis

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Authors	Title	Year	Source title
Kornelius L., Wamelink J.W.F.	The virtual corporation : Learning from construction	1998	Supply Chain Management
Agapiou A., Flanagan R., Norman G., Notman D.	The changing role of builders merchants in the construction supply chain	1998	Construction Management and Economics
Saad M., Jones M., James P.	A review of the progress towards the adoption of supply chain management (SCM) relationships in construction	2002	European Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management
Xue X., Li X., Shen Q., Wang Y.	An agent-based framework for supply chain coordination in construction	2005	Automation in Construction
Xue X., Wang Y., Shen Q., Yu X.	Coordination mechanisms for construction supply chain management in the Internet environment	2007	International Journal of Project Management
Bankvall L., Bygballe L.E., Dubois A., Jahre M.	Interdependence in supply chains and projects in construction	2010	Supply Chain Management
Doran D., Giannakis M.	An examination of a modular supply chain : A construction sector perspective	2011	Supply Chain Management
Tennant S., Fernie S.	Organizational learning in construction supply chains	2013	Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management
Jonsson H., Rudberg M.	Classification of production systems for industrialized building: A production strategy perspective	2014	Construction Management and Economics

Conclusions

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- Growing interest for SCM in construction
- Consolidation of the different perspectives still in progress, the main journals are open to contributions using different perspectives
- The citation network shows a compact network, witnessing that authors from different fields cite each other
- Main path analysis highlights non-linear development of the core concepts: lack of the characteristics of a discipline
- The key question: **to what extent is the construction industry different from the other ETO industries?**

Limitations and further developments

- We focused our analysis on the keywords and citations
- Analyses are still descriptive and more in-depth analysis is required on the content of the papers
- Future developments of this work include the citation analysis at the journal level and a deeper analysis of the citation network, using the indicators of closeness and centrality
- An additional effort is required to clearly trace the most promising avenues for future research

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